

Stability and Thermodynamics of RH-124(4*n*-Butyl-4H-1,2,4 triazole) with Transition Metals

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Stepwise stability constants of the complexes of RH-124(4*n*-butyl-4H-1,2,4 triazole) with manganese(II), cobalt(II), nickel(II), copper(II) and zinc(II) were studied in aqueous medium at 25 and 35° at $\mu=0.05$ and $0.10M$. The changes in the values of free energy of formation (ΔG), enthalpy (ΔH) and entropy (ΔS) have been reported. The values of ΔG were more negative at 35° indicating that complex formation is facilitated at higher temperature. The ΔH and ΔS values indicate that complexes are entropy stabilized.

RH-124 is a systemic protectant fungicide for the control of wheat leaf rust in both spring and winter wheat. This compound falls in the class of the aromatic heterocyclics and its unique structure is discussed with reference to pyridine and pyrrole to which triazole is structurally related. Imidazole and its derivatives play an important role in biological processes because of their presence in histamine and histidine. The imidazole groups of histidine are indeed generally responsible for most of the buffering power of proteins in the human body.

Patra *et al*¹ observed the antifungal and anti-histaminic activities of the imidazoles ring as the histidine moiety function as ligand towards transition metal ion in variety of biologically important molecules including iron-heme systems, vitamin B₁₂.

The metal ions namely Mn(II), Co(II), Cu(II) and Zn(II) are important catalysts in a variety of enzymic reactions. In view of the importance of the micronutrient elements and the imidazoles, it was of interest to study their interaction. In the present paper stability constants and thermodynamic parameters for the complexes of Mn(II), Co(II), Ni(II), Cu(II) and Zn(II) with RH-124 have been determined by Bjerrum-Calvin^{2,3} pH titration technique as adopted by Irving-Rossotti^{4,5}.

Experimental

The aqueous solutions of Mn(II), Co(II), Ni(II), Cu(II) and Zn(II) were obtained from chlorides of BDH 'AnalaR' grade and standardised. The strength of each solution was reduced to $0.01M$ by dilution. An aqueous solution of perchloric acid 'AnalaR' BDH was prepared and standardised against a standard alkali to get $0.05M$ solution of the acid. The solution of RH-124 ($0.05M$) was prepared in water. Standard solution of KClO₄ was used to maintain

the ionic strength. Standard carbonate free potassium hydroxide solution ($0.1M$) was used for titration. The double glass distilled water free from carbon dioxide was used for preparing the solutions.

"Systronics" model 322-1 pH meter with a glass and calomel electrode assembly was used for pH measurements during the titrations. Before starting the experiments the pH meter was calibrated with (BDH) buffer solutions (pH 4 and 7).

"SICO" type TBS thermostatic water bath was fitted with toluene regulators, electrical stirrer and electrical heaters. The electronic relay was used to maintain the temperature constant within $\pm 0.1^\circ$. All reagents were maintained at the temperature of the thermostatic water bath.

The following solutions (initial total volume 20 ml) were titrated against the standard alkali solutions ($0.1M$ KOH).

- A. 20 ml of $0.05M$ HClO₄
- B. A + 2.0 ml of $0.05M$ ligand
- C. B + 2.0 ml of $0.01M$ metal ion

All titrations were performed after adjusting the proper ionic strength and temperature, in a constant temperature water thermostat. The calculated quantities of one molar potassium perchlorate solutions, were employed to establish the ionic strength at 0.05 and $0.10M$. The plots of pH versus the volume of alkali required to reach the corresponding pH changes were plotted. The shapes of the titration curves were usual ones.

Results and Discussion

Proton-ligand stability constant: RH-124 (4*n*-butyl-4H-1,2,4 triazole) having structural formula(I)

is a heterocyclic compound, which is moderately strong organic base, capable of accepting—

protons at N-1 or N-2 and it also behaves as a very weak acid capable of releasing a proton when RH-124 was titrated against HCl, one mole of HClO₄ was needed for one mole of RH-124, the addition of only one proton to N-1 or N-2. The RH-124(I) will now become as (II).

The values of proton ligand stability constants at different temperatures and ionic strengths obtained by Irving and Rossotti method^{4,5} are given in Table 1.

TABLE 1—PROTON LIGAND STABILITY CONSTANTS OF 4n-BUTYL-4H-1,2,4 TRIAZOLE

Temperature °C	Ionic strength	log K ₁ ^H
25	0.05	4.55
	0.10	3.95
35	0.05	4.30
	0.10	4.17

Metal-ligand stability constants: The formation function \bar{n} and pL data pairs were calculated from the pH titration curves in the usual way^{4,5}. The values of stability constants were obtained from the formation curves using various methods, namely (A) half \bar{n} method, (B) least squares treatment and (C) elimination method⁶ which are in close agreement. The average values of the stability constants obtained are given in Table 2.

The values of \bar{n} lies between 0 and 2 showing thereby that these metals form 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 type of complexes with RH-124.

A comparison of the stability constants of these metal complexes shows that the sequence of stability is Zn(II) > Mn(II) > Co(II) > Cu(II) > Ni(II). It is apparent that the Irving William's natural order Zn(II) < Cu(II) > Ni(II) > Co(II) > Fe(II) > Mn(II) is not obeyed. A considerable deviation has been observed in the case of Zn(II), Mn(II) and Co(II). Kakkar *et al*⁶ and Mukerjee and Rawat⁷ reported higher stability of Co(II) complexes analogous to that of Cu(II) complexes.

TABLE 2—STABILITY CONSTANTS OF METAL RH-124 (4n-BUTYL-4H-1,2,4 TRIAZOLE) AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURES AND IONIC STRENGTHS

Metal ion	Constant	T=25°		T=35°	
		$\mu=0.05$	$\mu=0.10$	$\mu=0.05$	$\mu=0.10$
Mn ²⁺	log k ₁	3.81	2.90	4.81	2.98
	log k ₂	2.54	2.42	4.01	2.11
	log β_2	6.35	5.32	8.82	5.04
Co ²⁺	log k ₁	2.67	2.68	3.75	4.78
	log k ₂	2.33	2.53	2.08	3.16
	log β_2	5.00	5.21	5.83	7.89
Ni ²⁺	log k ₁	2.74	2.75	3.62	3.77
	log k ₂	2.11	2.31	2.13	1.99
	log β_2	4.85	5.06	5.75	5.76
Cu ²⁺	log k ₁	2.54	2.58	3.65	2.71
	log k ₂	2.37	2.54	3.42	—
	log β_2	4.91	5.12	7.07	—
Zn ²⁺	log k ₁	3.70	2.81	4.35	4.18
	log k ₂	2.71	2.43	4.23	4.68
	log β_2	6.41	5.24	8.58	9.21

The stability of Zn(II) and Mn(II) seems to be held up by the ligand through coordination or covalent bonding. So it may be due to forces involved in the formation of complexes which are not similar in all the cases.

The comparison of the stability constants at 25° and 35° at $\mu=0.05, 0.10M$ (Table 2) shows that the stability gradually increases with the rise in temperature. Thus it is evident that the reactions are more favourable and more stable complexes are formed at higher temperatures.

The stabilities for Mn(II) and Zn(II) complexes at 25° and 35° (Table 2) with the increase in the ionic strength of the medium results in a decrease in the stabilities and thus it is in agreement with the finding of Debye⁸. In case of Co(II), Ni(II), Cu(II) complexes at 25° and 35° an increase in the ionic strength of medium results in an increase in the stabilities. A qualitative explanation is the less dissociation of complex or in terms of the easy replacement of water molecules surrounding the cation. Coll *et al*⁹ reported the stability of FeCl²⁺ in perchlorate solutions that increased stability of the chloro complex was due to dehydrating action of perchlorates. Such a trend can be expected because combination of iron(III) with chloride ion to give FeCl²⁺ must be preceded by the partial removal of the hydration sphere from reactants. Thus in the present case there may be removal of water molecules from the hydration sphere during the formation of complexes.

Thermodynamic parameters :

The free energy of formation (ΔG), enthalpy changes (ΔH) and entropy changes (ΔS) associated with equilibrium shown in eq. (1) are reported at 25° and 35° at ionic strength of 0.05 and 0.10M.

where M^{2+} represents the metal ions i.e., Mn(II), Co(II), Ni(II), Cu(II), Zn(II). A^{m-} represents the RH-124. The following relationships (eq. 2-4) were used to derive the thermodynamic parameters :

$$\Delta G = -2.303 RT \log \beta \quad \dots (2)$$

$$\frac{d \ln \beta}{dt} = \frac{\Delta H}{RT^2} \quad \dots (3)$$

$$\Delta G = \Delta H - T \Delta S \quad \dots (4)$$

The values of ΔG , ΔH and ΔS are given in Tables 3-5. The values of free energy (ΔG) are negative, which suggest that greater the negative value, more stable is the complex. The free energy changes ($-\Delta G$) have higher values at 35° than at 25° . This shows that complex formation is facilitated at higher temperature.

It is seen that the reaction of RH-124 with metal ions Co(II), Ni(II), Cu(II), Zn(II) at $\mu=0.05$ and $0.10M$ and Mn(II) at $\mu=0.05M$ are endothermic showing that the enthalpy decrease is not favourable for the formation of these complexes, which means that the formation of such complexes takes place with absorption of energy. However, the complexes are stabilized by very large entropy increase.

TABLE 3—FREE ENERGY OF METAL -4n-BUTYL-4H-1,2,4 TRIAZOLE COMPLEXES AT DIFFERENT IONIC STRENGTHS AND TEMPERATURES (K cal/mole)

Metal ion	Free Energy	T=25°		T=35°	
		$\mu=0.05M$	$\mu=0.10M$	$\mu=0.05M$	$\mu=0.10M$
Mn ²⁺	— ΔG_1	5.195	3.954	6.779	4.129
	— ΔG_2	3.463	3.300	5.751	2.974
	— ΔG_3	8.658	7.254	12.430	7.103
Co ²⁺	— ΔG_1	3.641	3.655	5.285	6.666
	— ΔG_2	3.177	3.450	2.931	4.454
	— ΔG_3	6.818	7.105	8.716	11.120
Ni ²⁺	— ΔG_1	3.736	3.736	5.102	5.314
	— ΔG_2	2.877	3.286	3.002	2.804
	— ΔG_3	6.613	7.022	8.104	8.118
Cu ²⁺	— ΔG_1	3.464	3.518	5.144	3.819
	— ΔG_2	3.232	3.464	4.820	—
	— ΔG_3	6.696	6.982	9.964	—
Zn ²⁺	— ΔG_1	5.045	3.832	6.131	5.820
	— ΔG_2	3.695	3.312	5.991	5.750
	— ΔG_3	8.740	7.144	12.122	11.570

It is observed that values of ΔH and ΔS are negative for Mn(II) complexes at $\mu=0.1M$ which indicates that only ΔH is favourable for complexation. The negative values of ΔS suggest that

it retains the primary hydration sphere and the complexes are of outer sphere ion pair type.

TABLE 4—ENTHALPY CHANGES OF METAL-4n-BUTYL-4H-1,2,4 TRIAZOLE COMPLEXES (K cal/mole)

Metal ion	Ionic Strength	ΔH_1	ΔH_2	ΔH^*
Mn ²⁺	0.05	42.000	61.740	103.740
	0.10	1.260	-13.020	-11.760
Co ²⁺	0.05	45.860	-10.500	34.860
	0.10	86.100	26.460	112.560
Ni ²⁺	0.05	36.960	0.840	37.800
	0.10	42.940	-12.440	29.400
Cu ²⁺	0.05	46.620	44.100	90.720
	0.10	5.460	—	—
Zn ²⁺	0.05	27.300	68.840	91.140
	0.10	55.440	69.300	124.740

* $\Delta H = \Delta H_1 + \Delta H_2$ calculated from formation constants at 25° and 35° .

TABLE 5—ENTROPY OF METAL -4n-BUTYL-4H-1,2,4 TRIAZOLE COMPLEXES IN cal/deg/mole AT $\mu=0.05M$

Metal ion	T°C	ΔS_1	ΔS_2	ΔS
Mn ²⁺	25	158.372	218.802	377.174
	35	158.373	218.802	377.174
Co ²⁺	25	164.432	-24.573	139.859
	35	164.431	-24.574	139.857
Ni ²⁺	25	136.363	12.473	149.036
	35	136.564	12.474	149.038
Cu ²⁺	25	168.067	158.832	326.899
	35	168.064	158.831	326.896
Zn ²⁺	25	108.540	226.627	335.167
	35	108.542	226.724	335.266

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